

Chaos-based Image Assessment for THz Imagery

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Abstract – Multiscale image processing is a powerful technique that can determine image characteristics (e.g. clutter), provide denoising, and determine object features. Imagery is highly nonstationary (i.e. mean and variance change with location and time) and multiscaled (i.e. dependent on the spatial or temporal interval lengths). In this paper, we utilize the scale-dependent Lyapunov exponent (SDLE), which unifies the principles of fractal and chaos theory, to characterize the different signal behaviors on a wide range of scales simultaneously. Commonly used complexity measures, including those from information theory, chaos theory, and random fractal theory, can all be related to the values of the SDLE at specific scales, and therefore, SDLE can act as the basis for a unified theory of multiscale analysis of complex imagery data. We describe the power-law and singular-value decomposition (SVD) for image processing and demonstrate a SDLE example using TeraHertz (THz) imagery for concealed target image fusion.

Keywords: Image Processing, scale-dependent Lyapunov exponent, TeraHertz, singular-value decomposition

1 Introduction

Significant work on image processing covers a broad spectrum of analysis; including target exploitation, image fusion; and video processing. For some types of imagery, there is a need to analyze the multiscale and heavy-tail nature. We utilize a novel technique in multiscale imagery analysis using the *SDLE* [1] of the singular-value decomposition components of THz images.

Image fusion is an important research area [2, 3]. With the numerous image fusion methods, it is important to determine the quality of the image based on a set of standardized metrics [4, 5, 6]. Image fusion is an important component of many applications such as non-destructive evaluation (e.g. eddy current and ultrasonic [7]), night vision [4] and target tracking [8] (e.g. visual and infrared [9]), medical diagnosis (e.g. PET and MRI [10, 11]), and electro-optical (multispectral) targeting [12].

One appealing aspect of image fusion is its natural biological extension of the visual spectrum. The human cognitive interest in image fusion over a variety of sensor modalities must be appropriately assessed to ensure the perceptual fused image quality [13]. Our interest is to determine which metrics are best for different applications, image types, image fusion techniques, and

image defects (e.g. distortion, variance, and resolution). [4] For this paper, we are interested in processing THz imagery data that has shown promise for standoff concealed weapons testing, nondestructive evaluation, and medical diagnosis. The available images include visual spectrum data, and THz images collected with no obstruction (normal) and clothing obscurations with a loss (attenuation only) of 30 percent (minus 30) [14, 15]. Figure 1 shows the image result from the raw signals from the THz images [14, 15] of which we will fuse the THz images that simulates a concealed detection analysis.

Figure 1. Image Data: Visual(left), THz (Right). [14-15]

Being able to fuse THz imagery can add additional context to concealed object detection but is a function of operating conditions [16]. For example, using road information for targeting tracking and identification methods [17, 18] are analogous to human physical models to locate weapons. Bio-inspired image fusion methods can be applied to feature extraction [19] and frequency analysis [20] to support concealed weapon detection.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 overviews the multiscale analysis using the SDLE. We first define SDLE, then apply it to characterize low-dimensional chaos, noisy chaos, and random processes with *decaying power spectral density* (the so-called $1/f^\alpha$ processes). As real world application, Section 3 discusses the image fusion metrics and we apply SDLE to characterize THz data for analysis of image content. Section 4 provides the conclusions.

2 Multiscale Image Analysis

Complex imagery collections usually are comprised of multiple subsystems that exhibit both highly nonlinear deterministic, as well as, stochastic (i.e. random) characteristics, and are regulated hierarchically. These systems generate signals, $x(n)$, that exhibit complex characteristics such as sensitive dependence on small

disturbances, long memory, extreme variations, and nonstationarity. A random process S , is characterized by its power spectral density $S(f)$, where f is the frequency. Noise fluctuations are typically modeled as $1/f^\alpha$, where α [$1 < \alpha < 3$] characterizes the correlation structure of the increment process, where $\alpha < 1$ is an increment process with correlation. Depending on whether $H=(\alpha-1)/2$ is larger than, equal to, or smaller than $1/2$, the increment process is said to have persistent long-range correlation, short-range or no correlation, and anti-persistent correlation. In particular, $\alpha=2$ corresponds to Brownian motion, whose increment process is the white Gaussian noise. [1]

While the multiscale nature of signals cannot be fully characterized by existing stationary signal processing methods, the nonstationarity of the data is even more troublesome, because it prevents direct application of spectral analysis, or methods based on chaos theory and random fractal theory. For example, in order to reveal that the data is of $1/f$ nature [21, 22] with anti-persistent long-range correlations [23, 24] and multifractality [25], time series has to be preprocessed to remove components (such as the oscillatory ones) that do not conform to fractal scaling analysis.

Rapid accumulation of complex imagery data has made it increasingly important to be able to analyze multiscale and nonstationary data. Since multiscale signals behave differently, depending upon the temporal and spatial scale at which the data are examined, it is of fundamental importance to develop measures that explicitly incorporate the concept of scale so that different data behaviors on varying scales can be simultaneously characterized.

Straightforward multiscale analysis include short-time Fourier transform based time-frequency analysis, wavelet analysis, and time-domain adaptive filtering. Multiscale analysis can also be based on chaos theory and random fractal theory [26], such complex communication data [27], financial data [23-25], and cardiology data [1, 26]. Complex multiscale analysis has been used for imagery data [e.g. visual [28, 29], radar [30, 31, 32]) and communications [33].

The key element of random fractal theory is *scale-invariance*. Therefore, fractal methods are among the simplest multiscale approaches—only one or a few parameters are sufficient to describe the complexity of the signal across a wide range of scales where the fractal scaling laws hold. The major multiscale analysis methods evolved from chaos theory include ε -entropy [34], the finite size Lyapunov exponent (FSLE) [35, 36, 37], multiscale entropy (MSE) [38], and the scale-dependent Lyapunov exponent (SDLE) [26]. Conceptually, SDLE is inspired by FSLE. Computationally, SDLE is based on the time dependent exponent curves [39]. The major difference between FSLE and SDLE is that FSLE assumes divergence in the underlying dynamics while SDLE does not. As a result, FSLE has to be positive, while SDLE can assume any value. Consequentially, SDLE possesses a

unique scale separation property, which allows it to readily deal with nonstationarity and detect intermittent chaos, while FSLE does not. Here, we use the SDLE as a unified theory for the multiscale analysis.

2.1 Scale-dependent Lyapunov exponent (SDLE)

Chaos theory is a mathematical analysis of irregular behaviors of complex systems generated by nonlinear deterministic (i.e. future behavior described by the initial conditions) interactions of only a few degrees of freedom without concern of noise or intrinsic randomness. Random fractal theory, on the other hand, assumes that the dynamics of the system are inherently random. One of the most important classes of random fractals is $1/f^\alpha$ processes with long-range correlations. Therefore, the foundations of chaos theory and random fractal theory are entirely different. Consequentially, different conclusions may be drawn depending upon which theory is utilized to analyze a data set. In fact, much of the research in the past has been devoted to determining whether a complex time series is generated by a chaotic or a random system [1, 39, 40, 41]. From past research, $1/f^\alpha$ processes have distinguished themselves as providing counter examples that invalidate commonly used tests for chaos [42, 43, 44]. The two research communities, one favoring chaos theory, the other random fractal theory, are constantly debating with each other as to the applicability of their theories. While this classic issue, distinguishing chaos from noise, is still important, the authors believe that chaos and random fractal theories should be used synergistically, instead of individually, in order to comprehensively characterize the behaviors of signals on a wide range of scales. Based on this belief, we aim to develop a complexity measure that can not only effectively distinguish chaos from noise, but also be able to readily extract the crucial or the defining parameters of a process generating the data, be it chaotic or random. SDLE appears to have the capability to model systems with and without chaotic noise.

SDLE stems from two important concepts, the time-dependent exponent curves [39] and the finite size Lyapunov exponent [26, 35-44, 45].

2.2 SDLE Computation

We assume that all that is known is a scalar time series $x[n] = x(1), x(2), \dots, x(n)$. Regardless of whether the dynamics are chaotic or random, we use time delay embedding [46] to form vectors:

$$V_i = [x(i), x(i+L), \dots, x(i+(m-1)L)] ;$$

$$i = 1, \dots, N_p = n - (m-1)L, \quad (1)$$

where the embedding dimension m and the delay time L are chosen according to certain optimization criteria [29]. When the time series is random, such a procedure transforms the self-affine stochastic process into a self-similar process in phase space. The phase-space represents all possible system states as unique points. In this case,

however, the specific values of m and L are not important, so long as $m > 1$ to validate the phase space

Figure 2. A schematic showing 2 arbitrary trajectories in a general high-dimensional space, with the distance between them at time 0, t , and $t + \delta t$ being ε_0 , ε_t , and $\varepsilon_t + \delta t$, respectively. Using the notation of Eq. (1), ε_0 and ε_t amounts to $\|V_i - V_j\|$ and $\|V_{i+t} - V_{j+t}\|$, respectively.

After a proper phase space is re-constructed, we consider an ensemble of trajectories. We denote the initial separation between two nearby trajectories by ε_0 , and their *average separation* at time t and $t + \Delta t$ by εt and $\varepsilon t + \Delta t$, respectively. The trajectory separation is schematically shown in Figure 2. We then examine the relation between ε_t and $\varepsilon_t + \Delta t$, where Δt is small. When $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, we have,

$$\varepsilon_{t+\Delta t} = \varepsilon_t e^{\lambda(\varepsilon t) \Delta t}, \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda(\varepsilon t)$ is the SDLE. $\lambda(\varepsilon t)$ is given by

$$\lambda(\varepsilon_t) = \frac{\text{Ln } \varepsilon_{t+\Delta t} - \text{Ln } \varepsilon_t}{\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

Equivalently, we have a differential equation for ε_t ,

$$\frac{d \varepsilon_t}{dt} = \lambda(\varepsilon_t) \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Given a time series data, the smallest Δt possible is the sampling time τ .

Note that the classic algorithm of computing the Lyapunov exponent λ_1 [47] amounts to assuming $\varepsilon_t \sim \varepsilon_0 e^{\lambda_1 t}$ and using an average of $(\text{Ln } \varepsilon_t - \text{Ln } \varepsilon_0)/t$ to estimate λ_1 . Depending on ε_0 , this may not be true for completely chaotic systems. This is emphasized in the schematic of Figure 2 — $\varepsilon_t + \delta t$ could in fact be smaller than ε_t . A greater difficulty with such an assumption is that for any type of noise, λ_1 can always be greater than 0, leading to misclassifying noise as chaos. The reason is typically explained as: ε_t will be closer to the most probable separation, or “diameter”, of the “attractor”, so long as ε_0 is small. On the other hand, Eq. (2) does not involve any assumptions, except that Δt is small. As we will see, chaos amounts to $\lambda(\varepsilon)$ being almost constant over a range of ε .

To compute SDLE, we start from an arbitrary number of shells,

$$\varepsilon_k \leq \|V_i - V_j\| \leq \varepsilon_k + \Delta \varepsilon_k, \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \quad (5)$$

where V_i, V_j are reconstructed vectors, ε_k (the radius of the shell) and $\Delta \varepsilon_k$ (the width of the shell) are arbitrarily chosen small distances ($\Delta \varepsilon_k$ is not necessarily a constant).

We then monitor the evolution of all of the pairs of vectors (V_i, V_j) within a shell and take the average. Assuming that taking logarithm and averaging can be exchanged, Eq. (3) can now be written as

$$\lambda(\varepsilon_t) = \frac{\langle \text{Ln } \|V_{i+t+\Delta t} - V_{j+t+\Delta t}\| - \text{Ln } \|V_{i+t} - V_{j+t}\| \rangle}{\Delta t} \quad (6)$$

where t and Δt are integers in units of the sampling time, and the angle brackets denote the average within a shell.

Note that the initial set of shells for computing SDLE serve as initial values of the scales; through evolution of the dynamics, the shells will automatically converge to the range of inherent scales — which are the scales that define Eqs. (3) and (4). Also note that when analyzing chaotic time series, the condition

$$|j - i| \geq (m - 1)L, \quad (7)$$

needs to be imposed when finding pairs of vectors within a shell. Eq (7) eliminates the effects of tangential motions [41] and affords an initial scale to converge to the inherent scales [28].

To better understand the notion of “inherent scales”, it is beneficial to discuss the notion “characteristic scale” (or “limiting scale”), ε_∞ , defined as the scale where SDLE is close to 0. If one starts from $\varepsilon_0 \ll \varepsilon_\infty$, then, regardless of whether the data is deterministically chaotic or simply random, εt will initially increase with time and gradually settle around ε_∞ . Consequentially, $\lambda(\varepsilon_t)$ will be positive before εt reaches ε_∞ . On the other hand, if one starts from $\varepsilon_0 \gg \varepsilon_\infty$, then εt will simply decrease, yielding negative $\lambda(\varepsilon_t)$, again regardless of whether the data are chaotic or random. When $\varepsilon_0 \sim \varepsilon_\infty$, then $\lambda(\varepsilon_t)$ will stay around 0. Note however, that ε_∞ may not be a single point, but a function of time, such as a periodic function of time. These discussions make it clear that chaos can only be observed on scales much smaller than ε_∞ .

To better understand SDLE, we now point out a relation between SDLE and the largest positive Lyapunov exponent λ_1 estimated for a true chaotic signal using, say, the Wolf *et al.*'s algorithm [37, 48]. It is given by [26]

$$\lambda_1 = \int_0^{\varepsilon^*} \lambda(\varepsilon) p(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon \quad (8)$$

where ε^* is a scale parameter (e.g., for re-normalization when using Wolf *et al.*'s algorithm [37, 48]), $p(\varepsilon)$ is the probability density function for the scale ε given by

$$p(\varepsilon) = Z [dC(\varepsilon) / d\varepsilon], \quad (9)$$

where Z is a normalization constant satisfying $\int p(\varepsilon) d\varepsilon = 1$, and $C(\varepsilon)$ is the well-known Grassberger-Procaccia's correlation integral [42]. Note that the lower-bound for the integration is set to be zero here. In practice, on scales smaller than ε_{min} , the probability $p(\varepsilon)$ will be zero. Therefore, one could replace the lower-bound for the integration by ε_{min} .

SDLE also has distinct scaling laws for deterministic chaos, noisy chaos, random Levy processes, stochastic oscillations, and complex motions with multiple scaling laws on different scale ranges [26, 38]. Gao *et. al.*, [29] assessed $1/f^\alpha$ noise using a principle component analysis (PCA) for imagery. Here, we seek to integrate PCA (or SVD) with SDLE as SVD determines the key components of the image versus all pixel intensity values.

3 Image Processing Example

Image analysis focuses on three areas: image registration, image fusion, and image fusion performance assessment. In this example, we investigate the multiscale analysis over various THz images taken at different obscurations as shown in Figure 1 to determine multi-scaling content.

3.1 Image Analysis

Image registration [48, 49] is required for image fusion as shown in Figure 3. By aligning the pixels, overlay fusion can be done of the images to display to the user. Likewise, if the images are aligned, then signals detected or features extracted from each separate image can be linked in space. Finally, image segmentation and entity classification can be enhanced by using the corresponding areas in each image to validate potential areas of interest.

Figure 3. Image Fusion Analysis.

3.2 Image Fusion Performance Evaluation

There are many types of image fusion routines that include wavelets, spatial overlap, and multiresolution techniques [2, 3]. Image Fusion is categorized into spatial and transform domain methods to improve multiresolution image sharpening and spectral and spatial image content [50]. Spatial-domain methods enhance the spectral domain, but suffer from spatial distortion in the fused image. Transform-domain methods show a better performance in spatial and spectral quality. A summary of image fusion method comparisons was conducted in [3]. From the initiation of the *Universal Image Quality Index* (UIQI) [51] image fusion performance evaluation includes multiresolution and multiscale techniques for target recognition. [52, 53, 54].

3.3 THz Image Analysis

Form the test images, we see that the normal (no obscuration) provides content of the object. By increasing the obscuration (minus 30), we see that there some lost content in the image. The lost content would minimize the target analysis through pattern recognition. Figure 4(A) plots a portion of the images showing the different content. Comparing the two THz images, there is a difference in the probability distribution function (pdf) as

demonstrated in Figure 4(B). The goal was to a find power-law representation of the imagery; however since some pixel values are negative a power law analysis is not attainable. Nevertheless, the pdf is highly non-Gaussian. It is noted that the pdf captures the heavy-tail nature of the THz imagery. Also, we analyzed the visual image and it had a uniform, and widely spread distribution. Thus, we concluded that the THz imagery had a nature of heavy-tail (self-similar) analysis that could be exploited by multiscale fractal/chaos methods [1]. The multiscale nature could be also possible through the many applications of wavelet processing to images. However, comparing the THz images, we see a good fit for multiscale analysis for the THz imagery.

Figure 4. (A) Power-law Imagery results and (B) probability distribution function analysis.

3.4 SVD Analysis

One method of image assessment is the singular-value decomposition (SVD) which is a linear algebra technique that decomposes a matrix (e.g. energy content in an image) into its key components. The key components help as a measure of error or image quality. [55] The matrices U , Σ , V , represent the image with a smaller set of values.

$$M = U \Sigma V^T \quad (10)$$

Where matrix U is an $m \times m$ orthogonal matrix $U = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_r, u_{r+1}, \dots, u_m]$ composed of column vectors u_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. These vectors form an orthonormal set:

$$u_i^T u_j = \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

And matrix V is an $n \times n$ orthogonal matrix $V = [v_1, v_2, \dots, v_r, v_{r+1}, \dots, v_m]$ of column vectors v_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, which form an orthonormal set:

$$v_i^T v_j = \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Here, Σ is an $m \times n$ diagonal matrix with singular values (SV) on the diagonal defined as:

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \sigma_r & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \sigma_{r+1} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & \dots & \sigma_n \\ 0 & \dots & & & & \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, σ_i s are called Singular Values (SV) of matrix \mathbf{M} . It can be proved that

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_r > 0, \text{ and } \sigma_{r+1} = \sigma_{r+2} = \dots = \sigma_n = 0. \quad (14)$$

We utilized the SVD to get a compact representation of the image for multiple scaling.

Using the SVD components (as per image compression) as inputs to the SDLE, we can assess effects of obscurations. The SDLE can also work to help us choose an optimal obscuration for the THz image (which has elements of self-similarity, heavy-tail, and extra components) for concealed weapons detection. Since the SDLE works over many scales, we will use the SVD analysis in the rest of the application.

From Figure 5, we see that the SVD of the images characterize some interesting attributes. Both of the THz images have significant decreasing image content and are shifted lower than the visual image, but have similar characteristics to the visual image. Use of the SVD parameters could help choose an optimal parameter selection to operate over the THz images for various unknown obscurations to increase the content for pattern recognition; however, a simple thresholding of the image did not aid in the analysis, so it is not considered in the SDLE analysis.

Figure 5. SVD Spectrum of Images.

3.5 SDLE Analysis over the SVD Images

Using the SDLE, we had to determine the analysis over many supporting parameters: the scaling, shell size, m , L , and the number of iterations. For this analysis, we used appropriate values and further work will examine any gain from optimizing the results over the various parameters. Figure 6, presents the results of the analysis.

The analysis of the image with the SDLE, while novel, presents some interesting results. The results are somewhat inherent in the SVD with the extra knowledge that the SDLE brings forth many powerful assessments that support information theory, entropy analysis, fractal (e.g. wavelets), and chaos analysis.

The plot shows that the THz imaging has an upward slope. The consistency of the slopes can serve as a useful indicator of image content (i.e. scaling) before pattern recognition.

Next, we see a commonality between the THz images except that the choice of obscuration affects the

consistency of the slope. With no obscuration, the SDLE plot is sporadic, having fluctuations before $\log \epsilon$ of -1. The minus30 obscuration has a consistent analysis. Even the general upward trend is similar, at low values of ϵ , there is a marked difference. Based on the sensor (THz), target (metal), and the environment (amount of obscuration); we can use the SDLE to determine an off-line trained image set for estimated obscuration for target recognition.

Figure 6. SDLE plot of THz Images.

4 Conclusions

There are many multiscale image analysis methods [56] available such as those featured in www.imagefusion.org (e.g. wavelet decomposition) and analyzed in [4]. The THz imagery, with target obscuration, requires a multiscale analysis of which we explored the use of SDLE. We found the SDLE applicable for THz images showing an analysis improvement from no obscuration to some obscuration. Specifically, we were looking at methods of processing THz imaging that could lead to pattern recognition where a target is obscured, but identifiable from a THz image. We have shown that the SDLE provides a powerful method to possibly choose between the obscuration parameters for a THz image collection and future work requires a comparison to other multiscale approaches. While this is a first application of the SDLE to images, there are many issues to consider for performance evaluation over sensors, targets, and environment. [57]

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